

FUNCTION INTEGRATED ARCH BRIDGE IN A RESOURCE-EFFICIENT LIGHTWEIGHT DESIGN

E. Rudolph¹, A. Ehrlich², S. Gelbrich³, M. Röhrkohl⁴ and L. Kroll⁵

¹Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Technische Universität Chemnitz
D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: enrico.rudolph@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

²Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Technische Universität Chemnitz
D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: andreas.ehrlich@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

³Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Technische Universität Chemnitz
D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: sandra.gelbrich@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

⁴Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Technische Universität Chemnitz
D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: meike.roehrkohl@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

⁵Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology, Technische Universität Chemnitz
D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

Email: lothar.kroll@mb.tu-chemnitz.de, web page: <https://www.leichtbau.tu-chemnitz.de>

Keywords: Arch bridge, Function integration, Lightweight design, Sandwich structure, Bridge monitoring

ABSTRACT

Nowadays free formed buildings with organic shapes and biomorphic structures in combination with resource and energy efficiency as well as functional integration are getting more and more in the focus of modern civil engineering. The Basis of such innovative buildings are conventional construction materials like steel, glass and reinforced concrete, whereby these classic materials are limited regarding requirements as degree of lightweight, freedom of design and efficiency as wells as functional integration. For this reason, innovative buildings often cannot be realised or only with high costs and expenditure of resources.

Within the scope of the research project “New lightweight structural components and processing technologies for the application in support structures”, supported by the Sächsische Aufbaubank SAB, the theoretical and experimental basis for a new function integrated, modular support structure in lightweight design was established.

The focus here was on the designs development of a support structure with integrated sensor technology for bridge monitoring and lighting control and its realization by the use of new production technologies. Especially the use of glass-fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP), because of their low weight, excellent mechanical properties and corrosion resistance as well as the possibility of a load-adjusted dimensioning, resulted in new solution approaches.

In connection with the realization of the production, different technological concepts were analyzed with reference to their suitability, integration of required force transmission and further functions during and after production. The analysis of the lightweight elements with regard to their production and their mechanical properties resulted in a holistic production and tool concept, which represents the whole process chain from the textile to the structural component. The transfer of the results into practice was done within the construction of a new function integrated lightweight arch bridge in Chemnitz.

1 INTRODUCTION

The focus of modern architecture is progressively on free-formed buildings and organic shapes. Therefore, form-finding process and design are conducted more and more via complex, computer-assisted methods [1]. The implementation of these form-finding process depends essentially on the performance of the material and is accompanied by new challenges. For the construction and operation of buildings, design aspects are as important as demands for load capacity, function integration and resource efficiency. Because of their complexity, these new restrictions cannot be complied by using conventional building materials alone. New approaches are required, which include the development of innovative lightweight materials by combining hardening, functional and shaping material structures [2].

Inspired by properties of natural lightweight structures, like marine algae and plant leaves, bionic approaches and natural structures are increasingly adapted for technical applications (fig. 1) [1, 3]. In modern architecture as well as in nature, efficient lightweight design is essential for bridging maximum spans [2]. Therefore, a material-saving and weight-reducing way of construction, with lightweight designs based on nature are focused. This is to be achieved by replacing heavy material with lightweight material.

The implementation of lightweight design thus involves lightweight material in combination with support structures that are dimensioned in a load-adjusted way. Efficient, functionally integrated material combinations are needed. Further research is necessary, particularly in the field of fiber-reinforced composite material for the application in civil engineering [4].

2 FROM THE FORM-FINDING-PROCESS TO MANUFACTURING

2.1 Form-finding-process and selection of material

The main challenge in the development of support structures in lightweight design for resource-efficient bridges was to realize maximum spans with a minimum of weight in structure and with materials of low density and with integrated functions like monitoring and lighting. Based on these key points, the design was conducted, the material selected and finally a reference object built.

The starting point of the form-finding-process was the workshop “Form-Finding: form follows material”, that accompanied the research project. In this workshop, architects worked out a lot of creative ideas and designs for innovative lightweight bridges. Particularly, the bridge design of the architectural firm Beier.Steiner Architekten und Ingenieure was selected to execute a closer examination of honeycomb support structures in bridge designs (fig. 1).

Figure 1: Bridge module

GFRP was selected as material for the bridge modules. In combination with the structure, chosen for the bridge design, this led to a support structure with low use of materials and low dead load. Translucent GFRP covers were used as filling material for the honeycombs. By the application of translucent GFRP covers in combination with integrated LED technology, different lighting scenarios can be realized.

GFRP is composite material and consists of a polymer matrix with glass fibers in a defined alignment. GFRP has many advantages for building complete support structures, given that design and production are appropriate for the material. GFRP is not only translucent, it is also resistant to environmental influences and many aggressive substances, such as de-icing salt [5]. GFRP combines very good mechanical properties and low weight [6]. When designed and produced in a load-specific way, it ages only to a small degree. Examinations of dynamically loaded laminates over a period of 30 years showed no negative changes in the supporting laminates [7]. Thus, extremely durable buildings can be produced that need only low maintenance.

2.2 Construction, design and optimization

Based on the idea to use a honeycomb as basic form for a new and innovative support structure in bridge elements, a honeycomb-sandwich was implemented into a feasible solution, appropriate to material and production (fig. 2). Inspired by lightweight constructions in nature, the honeycomb-sandwich structure was developed following the natural honeycomb. The natural honeycomb consists of evenly shaped hexagonal cells that are strung together and has an ideal ratio between wall material and volume. Due to its stiffening function, such structures are often used to stabilize constructions. With an optimal material input, honeycombs ensure a uniform distribution of force within the component and thus fulfill the requirements imposed on lightweight design.

The sandwich design was chosen for the implementation of the new innovative support structure. Sandwich structures are characterized by high second area moments and low dead load so that these structures are particularly favorable for components exposed to great bending strain. The honeycombs act as core material for transmitting shear forces and increasing the spaces between the covering layers, which are exposed to tension and pressure. In this way, the honeycombs contribute to an increase of the second area moment. Both core material and covering layers consist of GFRP (fig. 2). In this way, the honeycombs contribute to an increase of the second area moment.

Figure 2: GFRP honeycomb module in sandwich design.

For the preliminary design and optimization of the GFRP honeycomb module the finite element method (FEM) was used. The software ANSYS Workbench was applied for this purpose. The geometry model of the GFRP honeycomb module was conducted fully parametrically. That allows a fast adaptation of the geometrical situation and facilitates the calculation of different variant types in a minimum of time. The geometry of the single honeycombs (length, width, height) and their number in length and width can be modified via parameters to generate the GFRP honeycomb module. The module is divided into four elements (honeycomb core, upper and lower covering layer, module border) so that the thickness and material properties can be determined for each element separately (fig. 3).

Figure 3: Geometry for the simulation.

The discretization was realized with shell elements, to keep the computing time within acceptable limits. Especially with regard to the subsequent optimization, the computing time for a single run is very important, because many runs are necessary to get reliable results.

Based on the serviceability limit state and the ultimate limit state, combined load consisting of a surface load, a single load in the middle of the honeycomb and the dead load of the GFRP module was used for the preliminary design. The basis for the load combination is provided by DIN EN 1990 and DIN Technical Report 101. The bearing is realized by two edges of the GFRP module based on the later installation situation.

For the evaluation of the GFRP module the maximum principal stress, the maximum shear stress and the maximum deflection are analyzed, in accordance with the ultimate limit state and the serviceability state (fig. 4).

Figure 4: Framework conditions and results of the simulation.

The optimization of the GFRP module was carried out using a software integrated calculation algorithm. Therefore the parameters that are going to be optimized have to be activated, the framework conditions (loads, supports), stress and displacement limits have to be defined. After an adequate number of calculation runs, the optimization results in a GFRP honeycomb module with a set-up that is perfectly adapted to the defined conditions.

To verify the simulation, the results were compared to the values measured in pressure tests of single honeycombs (fig. 5). In those tests, the single honeycombs were loaded with a compression force of 10 kN on an area of 10 cm x 10 cm in the middle of the honeycomb. Tests and simulation showed a very good agreement of the shift values. With a deviation of 6 %, the simulation is very suitable for the preliminary design of the GFRP honeycomb modules.

Figure 5: Test and simulation of a single honeycomb.

Based on the simulation results of the preliminary design, the final structural dimensioning was conducted with the software Sofistik. Sofistik provides simple tools to display and calculate a variety of load combinations. However, the parameterization is extremely time-consuming, which justifies the splitting of the design process into preliminary design with ANSYS Workbench and final structural dimensioning with Sofistik.

2.3 Implementation of production

For the implementation of the production of the structural elements, two different technology concepts were developed and tested. The first concept includes the production of single honeycombs using the winding method, followed by agglutinating the single honeycombs to honeycomb modules (fig. 6).

Figure 6: Process chain from toolmaking to complete single honeycombs.

The winding method was chosen with regard to the dimensions of the components, the necessary reinforcing angle and the notified midsize batch. The mounting of the single honeycombs to honeycomb modules requires small tolerances within the single honeycombs to keep addition errors and significant deviations within the module at a low level. Producing the modules in the winding method is not feasible for curved bridges, because the effort regarding design and production of the different winding cores is too high.

The final concept includes the production of geometrically adjusted half-honeycombs in the wet-in-wet technology. The honeycomb core is made out of joint laminate strips in a meandering pattern, which are pressed into the wet-laminated cover layer afterwards (fig. 7).

Figure 7: Production of the modules from meander-formed laminate strips.

Due to their design, the laminate strips that are used for the production of the cores allow the production of different module types. The tool costs are reduced, compared to the production of the modules from single honeycombs, because fewer molds are needed to implement the curved modules.

For the pre-assembly of the honeycomb-core a mounting aid was developed to facilitate the agglutinating of the laminate strips (fig. 7). The mounting aid consists of a 60 mm thick multiplex board, into which the honeycomb pattern was cut with a CNC cutter to guarantee the required tolerances.

A further step in the production of the modules was the application of a slip-resistant wearing layer onto the cover layer, which is the walking layer of the lightweight honeycomb bridge (fig. 8). Different types of quartz sand with a different grain size were tested during the production of the single honeycombs to guarantee the required slip-resistance.

Figure 8: Application of a slip-resistant wearing layer.

2.4 Functional integration

A sensor system was integrated into the honeycomb module. It monitors the bridge and controls the integrated lighting (fig. 9). An integral sensor system was developed, which detects the position of pedestrians on the bridge and puts out the switching function for the automatic lighting of the bridge. The sensor system consists of embroidered sensor antennas, that are stitched onto a glass fiber pad in a spiral pattern. During the production of the bridge elements they are laminated into the cover layer [8].

The sensor antennas consist of insulated copper strands and are connected segmentally via a cascaded signal-processing unit (fig. 9). Combined with the sensor system a consistent lighting of the translucent GFRP honeycomb modules can be reached by the use of LED lights.

The electronics creates a localized electromagnetically field on the antennas, which allows a feedback after a change of the electrical resistance and/or the dielectricity. When a pedestrian steps on a sensor integrated bridge segment, the electrical resistance and dielectricity changes due to the isolating shoe and food. The resulting field characteristic of the sensor causes a switching function in the electronics unit. The electronics unit sends a signal to the control of the bridge and switches on the lighting.

Figure 9: Integrated sensor system for bridge monitoring and lighting control.

3 REFERENCE OBJECT

An innovative lightweight honeycomb bridge was developed and implemented in Chemnitz in the scope of a research project. It was built in the course of revitalization and reutilization of the former factory Haase into a company building and connects it with the opposite bank of the river Chemnitz. In accordance with the local situation, especially flood protection, the bridge was realized as a footbridge with a span of 30 m and a sidewalk width of 2.50 m.

Figure 10: Interactive honeycomb-bridge, Chemnitz

The shape and construction of the reference object comprises a bridge with an unequal round arch. The support structure consists of a steel support and a spanning tube turn. The curved sidewalk is mounted into the third points of the pavement construction, by means of two hanger pairs.

The sidewalk construction consists of torsion-free main girders lengthwise and function integrated lightweight honeycomb modules made of GFRP in transverse direction. The flat honeycomb structure acts as secondary support structure and lies between the steel girders. The sidewalk is embedded on both sides of the river by the use of massive abutments. A function integrated fairfaced concrete formwork was developed and applied.

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The focus in architecture and civil engineering are shifted increasingly to lightweight design because topics like saving of resources, freedom in design and functional integration become more and more important. Without a significant increase of resource efficiency, it is hard to realize future-oriented constructions. For the practical construction implementation of lightweight design in practical constructions, the materials and composites have to be highly effective and multi-functional. Fiber composites are ideally suited to meet these requirements.

Innovative, function integrated support structures in GFRP sandwich design with stiffening honeycomb cores have been developed within the scope of the research project. Thus, they are the basis for combining new innovative lightweight technologies and advanced functional design in support structures. Besides the use of GFRP honeycomb modules as secondary support structure in larger bridge structures with spans greater than 15 m the results of the research project will be mainly the basis for serial applications in smaller bridge structure with spans of up to 15 m. These support structures can be prefabricated in the factory. Due to the low weight of the precast structures, only small cranes are sufficient for the on-site mounting. This significantly increases the effectiveness of the mounting process.

Fiber composites have been further developed crucially in the last years, but they still were rarely used in civil engineering. The reason for this is in addition to the lack of experience of architects, planners and building authorities, especially in missing assured parameters for durability behavior, lack of standards, guidelines and approvals, as well as accepted test methods.

The aim of research and development now is to lay the groundwork for the application of fiber composites in support structures by developing innovative lightweight material composites, technologies for their production and integrating suitable sensors for monitoring. Therefore, a close cooperation of research, practice (building companies, architects, planners) and approving authorities is necessary. In this way, a couple of reference objects were implemented successfully in the last years. This is a significant step towards the approval of new lightweight materials and composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research project “New lightweight structural components and processing technologies for the application in support structures” was successfully realized thanks to the close cooperation between Fiber-Tech, Steelconcept, Hentschke-Bau, Stfi and TU Chemnitz. Great thanks also goes to the development fund provider Sächsische Aufbaubank SAB, the engineering office Schulze&Rank, Müller&Pfeiffer GmbH, the architects Beier.Steiner Architekten and engineers Dankhard Remmler, ARC Architekturconcept and Architekturkanal for supporting the project.

Europäische Union

Europa fördert Sachsen.

Europäischer Sozialfonds

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